

found to be 2.2×10^{-2} , 3.3×10^{-2} , 4.8×10^{-2} and $6.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation parameters E_a and ΔS^\ddagger have been computed from these rate constants employing the linear least-squares method and found to be $68.6 \pm 6.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-54.6 \pm 20.1 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Further, from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of Fig. 1, the values of K have been computed to be 15.2×10^{-2} , 25.4×10^{-2} , 33.3×10^{-2} and 45.0×10^{-2} at 50, 55, 60 and 65° respectively. These values are in good agreement with those calculated from the spectrophotometric data³, i.e. 11.7×10^{-2} , 16.3×10^{-2} , 28.2×10^{-2} and 45.7×10^{-2} at 50, 55, 60 and 65° respectively, thus furnishing further support to the proposed mechanism.

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Anodisation of Aluminium and some of its Alloys in Organic and Inorganic Acids

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THERE are numerous reports on the anodisation of Al, Al-Mg, Al-Zn and Al-Cu in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions at different current densities^{1,2}. The films formed at low current density (50.0 A m^{-2}) are organometallic in nature while at higher values ($200-400 \text{ A m}^{-2}$), the films are hard and compact¹.

In the present work, Al metal and Al-Mn and Al-Mg alloys were anodised at 1.0 A dm^{-2} and

$30 \pm 0.10^\circ$. The acids used for anodisation were; acetic, propionic, n-butyric, maleic, oxalic, citric, tartaric, phosphoric and sulphuric acids.

Experimental

The cleaning, anodisation, corrosion tests and chemical composition of specimens (Al and Al-Mn alloy) were described in our earlier publication³. The chemical composition of Al-Mg alloy used was Al, 94.70; Mg, 5.0; Fe, 0.1; Si, 0.1; Mn, 0.1%.

Results and Discussion

The temperature-time ($\Delta T-t$) relations were obtained from the dissolution process of the anodised and non-anodised specimens as shown in Fig. 1. It is obvious that the dissolution in HCl is characterised initially by a passive period of time

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔT vs t for Al in HCl anodised in different acids: (1) acetic, (2) propionic, (3) butyric, (4) maleic, (5) tartaric, (6) oxalic, (7) citric, (8) phosphoric and (9) sulphuric.

during which only a slight increase in temperature was observed which was then followed by an increase in temperature indicating the depassivation of the metal surface and the increase in the dissolution rate.

According to Mylius⁴, the reaction number is given by the relation, $R.N. = \Delta T_m / t$, where t is the time needed for the temperature to attain a maximum and ΔT_m the maximum elevation in temperature. The values of R.N. are given in Table 1. The observed decrease of R.N. corresponds to the increase in corrosion resistance caused by the anodic treatment. On the other hand, the time needed for the temperature to reach $\Delta T_m / 2$ ($t_{1/2}$) can be considered as a function of the corrosion resistance of the studied specimens. The values of $t_{1/2}$ are also given in Table 1. The specimens of Al anodised in polybasic carboxylic acids (oxalic, citric, tartaric and maleic) showed the highest values of $t_{1/2}$. This may be attributed to the gradual dissolution of the anodic film possessing a considerable thickness, which is obviously much greater than the thickness

NOTES

TABLE 1—(R.N.), $t_{1/2}$ AND RELATIVE DECREASE IN REACTION NUMBER (A) FOR ANODISATION OF Al, Al-Mn AND Al-Mg IN DIFFERENT ACIDS

Acid	Al			Al-Mn			Al-Mg		
	R. N.	$t_{1/2}$	% A	R. N.	$t_{1/2}$	% A	R. N.	$t_{1/2}$	% A
Non-anodised	2.68	19.0	—	7.56	6.0	—	6.85	6.0	—
Acetic	3.32	14.0	26.0	2.40	24.0	68.3	3.25	14.0	48.7
Propionic	0.67	41.0	74.3	2.18	28.0	71.2	5.50	6.5	13.1
n-Butyric	2.35	21.0	10.6	6.70	7.0	11.4	5.02	12.5	20.5
Maleic	1.50	38.0	42.9	2.40	24.5	68.8	1.54	37.0	75.7
Tartaric	0.84	68.5	68.0	1.33	48.0	82.4	1.18	49.0	81.4
Citric	0.50	89.5	81.0	1.57	38.5	79.2	3.19	45.0	49.6
Oxalic	0.73	78.0	72.2	1.23	51.0	83.7	1.70	37.5	73.1
Phosphoric	1.19	50.0	54.7	2.19	27.5	71.0	3.41	15.0	46.1
Sulphuric	0.86	75.5	69.7	1.71	36.7	77.4	2.57	22.0	59.4

of the film formed in other acids (monobasic). The same phenomenon was noticed for the anodised Al-Mn and Al-Mg alloys. The anodisation of Al in acetic acid gave a highly pitted surface which did not resist the attack of HCl. Thus, $t_{1/2}$ was found to be less than that of the non-anodised Al (Table 1). Anodisation of Al and Al-Mn in propionic acid led to the formation of a protecting anodic film (high $t_{1/2}$) while Al-Mg in the same acid produced a comparatively poor quality film with a $t_{1/2}$ very close to that of the non-anodised alloy. Anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg in either phosphoric or sulphuric acid yielded anodic films with higher values of $t_{1/2}$ close to those obtained for anodisation in polybasic carboxylic acids.

$\Delta T-t$ relation could be expressed over a wide range of temperatures by the empirical formula⁶, $t = a + 2.303 b \log \Delta T$, where a and b are constants, and $\Delta T = T - T_0$ at time t . The plots of $\log \Delta T$ vs t for anodised Al as a representative case are shown in Fig. 2. The values of a and b for the anodised and non-anodised specimens of Al are given in Table 2. The constant a represents the time needed for the temperature to reach $\Delta T = 1$, while b is the time

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log \Delta T$ vs t for Al anodised in different acids: (1) acetic, (2) propionic, (3) butyric, (4) maleic, (5) tartaric, (6) oxalic, (7) citric, (8) phosphoric and (9) sulphuric.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF a AND b CONSTANTS AND RELATIVE DECREASE IN CORROSION RATE (A) OF Al ANODISED IN DIFFERENT ACIDS

Acid	a	b_1	b_2	% A_1	% A_2	% A_3
Non-anodised	11.6	5.0	—	—	—	—
Acetic	3.5	7.0	—	0.0	28.6	—
Propionic	12.5	7.0	18.5	7.2	28.6	73.0
n-Butyric	13.0	5.0	—	10.8	0.0	0.0
Maleic	23.0	10.0	—	49.5	50.0	—
Tartaric	28.0	18.1	26.3	58.5	72.4	81.0
Citric	25.0	24.4	66.7	53.6	79.5	92.5
Oxalic	38.0	37.0	6.2	69.0	86.5	20.0
Phosphoric	39.0	7.1	—	70.3	29.6	—
Sulphuric	64.5	8.9	5.7	82.0	43.8	12.2

consumed in raising the temperature from 31° to 40° or to magnify ΔT ten times. The value of $1/a$ can be considered as a function of the corrosion rate of the most outer layers of the anodic film. Thus, the relative increase in corrosion resistance (A) of the specimens caused by anodisation can be given as $A_{\Delta T=0.5^\circ} = (1 - a/a') 100$, where a and a' are constants for the non-anodised and anodised specimens respectively. On the other hand, $1/b$ can be considered as a function of the dissolution rate of the internal layers of the anodic film or the metal itself. Therefore, $A_{\Delta T > 0.5^\circ} = (1 - b/b') 100$, where b and b' are constants for non-anodised and anodised specimens respectively. The values of A at $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ$ and at $\Delta T > 0.5^\circ$ are recorded in Table 2 for anodised Al in different acids as an example.

On comparing the relative decrease in R.N. values (Table 1) and the factor A obtained from the $\log \Delta T-t$ relation (Table 2), it is obvious that R.N. method is unable to discuss the role of the anodic film. $\log \Delta T-t$ relation can throw light on the effect of the anodisation process and the increase in the corrosion resistance caused by the anodic film in its several stages of formation (the internal and external layers). The straight lines shown in Fig. 2 exhibited breaks at certain values of ΔT . This indicates a change in the interacting phases. In most of the cases, the values of b (over the break-point) are smaller than those below it. This may indicate that the dissolution rate of the metal increases owing to great possibility of complete disappearance of the anodic film. The values of b

over the break-point are closed to those of the non-anodised metal. The value of ΔT at which the break-point takes place can be seen as a function of the thickness of the anodic film. The value of b below the break-point may be considered as a porosity-dependent factor, and greater the porosity the lower is the value of b .

During anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg in organic acids, the following competitive anodic reactions may take place: (i) anodic dissolution of the metal, (ii) oxygen evolution, (iii) oxidation of the metal to the oxide, (iv) Kolbe decarboxylation and coupling and (v) oxidation of the organic matter in solution. The Kolbe decarboxylation-coupling process was reported to proceed on Al during its anodisation in organic acids⁵. An evidence of this reaction is the formation of oily drops floated on the surface of the citric and tartaric acids during the anodisation of Al and its alloys under investigation. In the case of propionic, butyric and maleic acids, white fume was formed around the non-immersed part of the anode. The fume is probably the products of oxidation and decarboxylation of the organic acids⁶. Anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg in citric acid was accompanied with sparks arising between the anode and the acid solution. Anodisation of Al-Mn in tartaric acid showed the same phenomenon. The spark formation always left dark spots very similar to pittings. These spots may be the products of intensive oxidation of the organic acids.

The possible oxidation of the metal to the oxide during anodisation must lead to an increase in weight of the specimen. Anodisation of Al, Al-Mn and Al-Mg for 0.5 h in citric and tartaric acids at 1.0 A dm⁻² lead to the increase in the weight of each specimen by 0.0130–0.0156 g/20 cm². In other acids, the weight increased by (0.60–9.0) $\times 10^{-3}$ g/20 cm².

In addition to all the possible reactions mentioned above during the anodisation process, the complexation between the metals Al, Mn and Mg and the added acids is not ruled out.

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Polarographic and Cyclic Voltammetric Reduction of *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde Isonicotinoylhydrazone

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ISONICOTINOYLHYDRAZIDE derivatives of carbonyl compounds are used extensively as therapeutic agents¹⁻³. *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone is one such compound. The therapeutic action is generally related to the redox behaviour of the compound. Hence the polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies of the compound in solutions of pH 2–9; and 4 and 8 respectively have been made here to understand this redox behaviour.

Experimental

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone (*o*-O₂N-BAINH) prepared by the reported⁴ method was purified by repeated crystallisation from hot aqueous alcohol and characterised by its spectral data, m.p. 236° (lit. 235–36°). All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Current-voltage curves are recorded in Britton-Robinson buffer solutions (pH 2–9). A Elico CL-25 DC pen recording polarograph was used for recording current-voltage curves of hydrazone. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $t=3.0$ s, $m=1.93$ mg s⁻¹ at a height of 85 cm of mercury column in water under open-circuit conditions. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 4 and 8) using cyclic voltammetric unit consisting of an X-Y recorder (Model RE 0074), PARC 175 universal programmer and PARC 174-A polarographic analyser. Metrohm 9323 hanging mercury drop electrode, platinum wire electrode and saturated calomel electrode were used as working electrode, counter electrode and reference electrode respectively. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS OF *o*-O₂N-BAINH AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Medium: 20% aqueous DMF, [*o*-O₂N-BAINH]=4 $\times 10^{-4}$ M

pH	-E _{1/2} V vs SCE		
	First wave	Second wave	Third wave
2.0	0.18	0.63	0.84
3.0	0.21	0.75	0.90
4.0	0.26	0.81	0.96
5.0	0.31	0.90	1.06
6.0	0.36	0.98	1.14
7.0	0.42	1.08	1.24
8.0	0.48	1.17	1.29
9.0	0.56	1.24	—

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